

26 = 0.001) to M60. Satisfactory sedation was obtained from M15 to M60. After stopping the
27 infusion, all donkeys recovered successfully (7.1 ± 2.4 minutes). No adverse effects were
28 observed during and after the infusion. **Primary limitations:** No painful stimulus or surgical
29 procedure was performed. **Conclusions:** Combining remifentanil and xylazine at the doses used
30 caused adequate sedation and short recovery time. Remifentanil did not cause excitation in the
31 donkeys. Future studies are necessary to test the protocol with painful stimuli.

32 **Keywords:** Asinine; Equine; Remifentanil; Sedation.

33 **1 Introduction**

34 Donkeys (*Equus asinus*) are rustic animals whose importance is often neglected due to
35 their specific characteristics, both in morphophysiological and pharmacological perspectives,
36 as well as their temperament.¹ Thus, some studies have evaluated the effects of drugs on
37 donkeys^{2,3}. However, protocols for this species are still scarce.

38 It is common to associate drugs to chemically contain equines, avoiding the
39 complications and costs of general anesthesia. The adrenergic alpha₂-agonist drugs produce
40 sedation, analgesia, and muscle relaxation despite their adverse effects.⁴⁻⁶ Among adrenergic
41 alpha₂-agonists, xylazine is the shortest acting and may result in insufficient analgesia for some
42 surgical or outpatient procedures in monotherapy. In these circumstances, they are administered
43 in association with opioids or with local blocking techniques to improve analgesia.⁷

44 Opioids are useful in anesthesiology because of their ability to decrease sympathetic and
45 somatic responses to harmful stimulation.⁸ Combinations of an alpha₂-agonist with an opioid
46 in single or repeated administrations, or even as part of a peri anesthetic protocol, can provide
47 synergistic analgesic effects and good sedation. This association reduces the potential for
48 excitation at the level of the central nervous system.⁹

49 Remifentanil is an opioid derivative of phenylpiperidine, supplied as remifentanil
50 hydrochloride, a lyophilized powder. Animal studies indicate that the pharmacological
51 properties of remifentanil are similar to those of other potent μ -opioid receptor agonists, such
52 as alfentanil.¹⁰ Characterized as a potent opioid of ultra-short duration, its use has been
53 described in studies conducted in different species, where it was shown to be a safe drug,
54 producing minimal hemodynamic changes, in addition to its onset of action and rapid recovery
55 after cessation of use, regardless of the duration of its administration. Therefore, remifentanil

56 appears to be a highly titratable opioid, providing profound analgesia for very brief periods in
57 which analgesia is necessary or for prolonged periods without the concern of prolonged
58 recovery.^{8,12} Some studies describe its use in horses^{5,6,12}. However, the literature has no
59 information on the systemic effects of remifentanil in donkeys.

60 In this context, this study aimed to evaluate the physiological and sedative effects of
61 continuous intravenous infusion of remifentanil and xylazine in donkeys from the northeastern
62 region of Brazil. We hypothesized that adverse effects would be insignificant when associating
63 the drugs in low doses and continuous infusion, and the sedation protocol can be considered for
64 seasonal surgical procedures.

65

66 **2 Material and Methods**

67

68 *2.1 Animals*

69

70 The study conditions were submitted to and approved by the Animal Use Ethics
71 Committee (CEUA/UFERSA) under protocol number No. 42/22. Ten adult donkeys from the
72 northeastern region of Brazil, seven males and three females, aged 5.3 ± 2.2 years and weighing
73 120.4 ± 21.4 kg, were used. The animals were classified as healthy after clinical and laboratory
74 examination (blood count, urea, creatinine, aspartate aminotransferase, alanine
75 aminotransferase, and total proteins) for the inclusion criteria. A sample calculation was
76 performed based on a pilot study with three animals using the dose presented in the study with
77 horses⁶. The calculation was done using GPower 3.1.9.7. This calculation and the mean and
78 standard deviation of sedation of M5, alpha 0.05, and Power 0.8 were compared with the
79 constant 0 of M0. The animals were dewormed with ivermectin (Ivomec®, Boehringer

80 Ingelheim), associated with trichlorfon and mebendazole (Trichlorsil paste®, Vansil), and
81 vaccinated against rabies four weeks prior to the start of the study. The animals were housed in
82 groups of five, in pickets of 10 x 7 m in the open air, with shade, and fed with voluminous grass
83 (*Pennisetum purpureum*) and concentrate (ground corn, soybean meal, wheat bran, common
84 salt, and calcitic limestone) twice a day, with water *ad libitum*. The acclimatization to the new
85 environment took four weeks.

86

87 2.2 Experimental study

88

89 One day before the procedure, the animals were transferred to individual stalls. Prior to
90 the experiment, they were subjected to a 12-hour fast from solid food and had access to water
91 *ad libitum*.

92 Initially, the physiological parameters of respiratory rate (RR) by inspection of the costal
93 grid, capillary refill time (CRT), heart rate (HR) by cardiac auscultation, rectal temperature
94 (RT), mean arterial pressure (MAP), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure
95 (DBP) through a multiparametric monitor (multiparametric monitor, touch screen, Delta Life,
96 model DL1000), and gastrointestinal motility by auscultation, assessing intestinal borborygmus
97 in the dorsal and ventral quadrants of the right and left side, were evaluated at baseline (M0).
98 After M0, trichotomy and antisepsis of the jugular vein were performed for catheterization,
99 using a 16-gauge catheter coupled to a 3-way stopcock.

100 Subsequently, the animals received a 0.8 mg·kg⁻¹ bolus of xylazine (xylazine
101 hydrochloride 2%, Syntec®) administered within 60 seconds by infusion pump (RS700 VET,
102 RZVET®) and, after 3 minutes, continuous infusions of xylazine and remifentanil (remifentanil
103 hydrochloride, Eurofarma®) were initiated at the rates 0.65 mg/kg/h and 6 µg/kg/h,

104 respectively, and discontinued over 60 minutes after three minutes of the initial xylazine bolus
105 (Figure 1).

106

Figure 1. Linear representation of the beginning and end of xylazine and remifentanyl infusions in donkeys.

Adapted from Palarrols *et al.*, 2020.

107 The same physiological parameters evaluated at M0 (HR, RR, CRT, RT, MAP, SBP,
108 and DBP) were monitored every 5 minutes until 60 minutes after drug administration (M60).
109 Gastrointestinal motility was evaluated 15 min, 1h, 4h, 8h, and 24h after the infusions (M60).

110 The head height above the ground was measured using a tape measure graduated in
111 centimeters from 0 to 160 cm, which was fixed to the lateral bar of the physical containment
112 trunk to evaluate sedation. The distance between the ground and the mandibular symphysis was
113 measured before beginning the instrumentation, in an environment free of external stimuli,
114 considering the head height of the animal at M0. Sedation was also evaluated using a simple
115 descriptive scale, assessing the level of sedation and ataxia,^{5,13} with scores from 0 to 3 for both
116 items (Table 1).

Table 1: Simple descriptive scale (SDS) scoring system for sedation and ataxia (FUNCIA *et al.*, 2016)⁵.

SEDATION	
SCORE	SIGNS
0	No sedation. The animal is alert, with normal posture and response to contact with the evaluator. Normal objection to intervention.
1	Light sedation. Head lowered, facial muscles relaxed, and lower lip hanging. Some response to intervention.
2	Moderate sedation. Head lowered towards the floor and swinging the hind legs. Slight response to intervention.
3	Marked sedation. Tries or becomes recumbent. No response to intervention.
ATAXIA	
SCORE	SIGNS
0	No ataxia. The animal stands and walks normally; can rotate with force.
1	Mild Ataxia. The animal can walk, but with some lack of limb control.
2	Moderate ataxia. The animal can only walk with support, staggers, but avoids falling.
3	Marked ataxia. The animal cannot walk without danger of falling, staggers, falls, turns over.

117

118 The patient's quality and total recovery time were evaluated from the end of the
 119 infusions to the time the patient presented with a score of zero for sedation and minimal ataxia.

120 The sedation score was assessed every two minutes after stopping the continuous infusion of
 121 xylazine and remifentanil.

122 Any need for more drugs for sedation, decreased administration, or any unexpected
 123 effect would be reported from the first xylazine *bolus* until recovery.

124 *2.3 Statistical Analysis*

125 Data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum
 126 values using the SAS V8 statistical program (System for Windows - SAS Institute Cary, North
 127 California; USA). After verifying the parametric assumptions, statistical differences between
 128 the times studied (M0 – M60) were verified through analysis of a mixed-effects model for
 129 repeated measures (Proc Mixed of the SAS program) for each variable studied, followed by the
 130 Dunnett test. The baseline moment (T0) was used as the base comparison variable.
 131 Nonparametric data were analyzed using the method described by Friedman. The significance
 132 level considered was 5%.

133

134 **3 Results**

135

136 The sedation and ataxia obtained were satisfactory in all animals throughout the
 137 procedure, soon after xylazine administration. After 20 minutes, moderate ataxia and sedation
 138 were observed, with a median sedation and ataxia score of 2 for both parameters remaining
 139 throughout the procedure. The height of the head in relation to the ground was significantly
 140 lower (p = 0.001) at baseline during the entire infusion time (Table 2).

141

Table 2 - Mean ± standard deviation (SD) for sedation score, ataxia score, and head height of donkeys submitted to continuous infusion of remifentanyl and xylazine for 60 minutes.

Variables	Measures	M0	M5	M10	M15	M20	M30	M45	M60
Sedation score (0-3)	Mean	0	0.9	1.0	1.2	1.6	1.7	1.9	1.9
	± SD	± 0	± 0.6**	± 0.5**	± 0.4**	± 0.2*	± 0.5*	± 0.3*	± 0.3*
	Median	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	2
	Min - max	0 - 0	0 - 2	0 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2

Ataxia score (0-3)	Mean	0	0.8	1.0	1.1	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9
	± SD	± 0	± 0.6**	± 0.5**	± 0.6**	± 0.5*	± 0.5*	± 0.4*	± 0.3*
	Median	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	2
	Min - max	0 - 0	0 - 2	0 - 2	0 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2	1 - 2
Head height (cm)	Mean	83.0	28.7	28.78	18.11	16	17	16.56	14.44
	± SD	± 9.5*	± 28.3**	± 33.1**	± 25.3**	± 22.2**	± 21.3**	± 21.4**	± 17.3**
	Median	82.5	15	15	5	5	10	5	10
	Min - max	65 - 100	0 - 85	0 - 84	0 - 78	0 - 69	0 - 63	0 - 63	0 - 56

*, ** Different asterisks on the same line indicate statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$ - Dunnett).

142 HR decreased significantly ($p = 0.049$) ten minutes after xylazine administration and its
143 continuous infusion with remifentanyl (M10), while RR decreased significantly ($p = 0.001$) after
144 5 minutes of the xylazine bolus (M5). MAP ($p = 0.02$), SBP ($p = 0.04$), and DBP ($p = 0.03$)
145 decreased significantly from M15, while RT remained stable throughout the procedure (Table
146 3).
147

Table 3 - Mean values ± standard deviation (SD) for heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), mean arterial pressure (MAP), diastolic pressure (DBP), capillary refill time (CRT), and rectal temperature (RT) of donkeys submitted to continuous infusion of remifentanyl and xylazine in 60 minutes.

Variables	Measures	M0 [‡]	M5	M10	M15	M20	M30	M45	M60
HR (bpm)	Mean	44.4	40.9	39.8	39.3	39.5	37.1 ± 8.4	38	41.5
	± SD	± 6.2*	± 6.1*	± 7.9**	± 7.1**	± 9**	**	± 7.8**	± 13.6**
RR (bpm)	Mean	34.3	18.0	15.3	14.1	13.8	11	9.8	10.5 ± 6.3**
	± SD	± 7.6*	± 9.0**	± 7.8**	± 7.9**	± 6.5**	± 5.1**	± 5.7**	
†SBP (mmHg)	Mean	166.8	160.7	153.7	137.6	136.3	144.8	147.3	131.7
	± SD	± 23.5*	± 34.2*	± 28.5*	± 34.4**	± 28.3**	± 32.8**	± 39.9**	± 30.3**

†MAP	Mean	137.9	141.4	133.6	113.9	109.9	128.2	123.3	108.9
(mmHg)	± SD	±32.0*	±41.76 *	±31.3 *	±38.1 **	±32.4 **	±37.3 *	±35.9**	±33.8**
DBP	Mean	118.8	106.5	110.4	99.1	95.7	101	93.6	
(mmHg)	± SD	±41 *	±40.1 *	±30 *	±37.2 **	±30.5 **	±39.4 **	±27**	86.8 ±27**
†CRT	Mean	2.6		2.0		2.0	1.8 ± 0.6	1.7 ±0.4	
(sec)	± SD	±0.7*	2.1 ±0.4*	±0.2**	2.1 ±0.4*	±0.2**	**	**	1.8 ±0.3 **
RT	Mean	37	37.0	36.9	37	36.9	36.6	36.6	36.2 ± 0.8
	± SD	±0.4*	±0.6 *	±0.5 *	±0.5 *	±0.6*	±0.7*	±0.5*	*

† Friedman; ‡ Base moment used for comparison through Dunnett's test.

*, ** Different asterisks on the same line indicate statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$ - Dunnett).

148

149 All animals recovered from sedation with 7.1 ± 2.4 minutes after discontinuing the drugs
150 and could move with minimal signs of ataxia.

151 No adverse effects were observed during and after the infusion. Behavior, physiological
152 parameters (HR, RR, SBP, DBP, MAP, and RT), appetite, and gastrointestinal movements
153 remained stable compared to M0 after recovery from xylazine and remifentanil infusion.

154

155 4 Discussion

156

157 This study demonstrated that continuous infusion of xylazine and remifentanil can be
158 an option for sedating donkeys during standing procedures. Objective assessment and
159 quantification of sedation are difficult. There are currently no validated sedation scoring
160 systems for donkeys. The doses of xylazine and remifentanil were based on a previous study⁶
161 on horses. Although the association between alpha2-agonists and opioids has already been
162 studied in donkeys,^{14,15} this is the first study to use remifentanil; therefore, we chose to use the
163 same doses used in horses. A moderate degree of sedation was observed in a preliminary study

164 conducted with two horses, suggesting that higher doses of this association are unnecessary in
165 donkeys.⁶ The results obtained were satisfactory regarding sedation and ataxia, thus
166 corroborating what was described by Lizagarra and Castillo-Alcala¹⁴. These authors also used
167 an association of an alpha₂-agonist, xylazine, with an opioid, butorphanol, in donkeys and
168 considered the association appropriate for sedating these animals for clinical procedures.

169 In a study using the association of butorphanol with dexmedetomidine or xylazine for
170 seasonal unilateral ovariectomy, the authors reported that the donkeys obtained moderate to
171 severe sedation (score 2-3). Both protocols were indicated for performing standing procedures
172 for donkeys¹⁵. Although the opioid used is different from that of our study, the xylazine dose
173 chosen was lower (0.5 mg/kg bolus and 0.5 mg/kg/h). It was reduced to 0.32 mg/kg/h during
174 the continuous infusion, which leads us to believe that the combination of drugs caused an
175 effective sedation. Similar results have been found by other authors¹⁴ who associated xylazine
176 with different doses of butorphanol in a bolus. The donkeys' sedation was deeper and longer-
177 lasting when employing a dose of 0.04 mg/kg.

178 The depth of sedation was also objectively assessed using head height relative to the
179 ground, as reported in previous studies on horses.¹⁶ Although the difference in height between
180 the mentioned species is debatable, a significant lowering of the head was observed between
181 the basal time and the other evaluated moments in donkeys and horses. This also corroborates
182 the study of Dzikiti *et al.*¹⁶ Although sedation was effective and complementary doses of drugs
183 were not necessary, no painful stimulus or surgical procedure was performed, which can be
184 considered a study limitation. Pollarols *et al.*⁶ used the same protocol in two horses submitted
185 to seasonal laparoscopy; one of the animals required 0.25 mg/kg of xylazine to improve
186 sedation, which can probably suggest that complementary doses of xylazine are necessary to
187 improve the degree of sedation of animals in clinical and surgical situations.

188 There was little evidence of any serious cardiovascular or respiratory effects. Slowing
189 the heart rate is a well-known effect of adrenergic alpha-2 agonists.¹⁷ However, this decrease
190 was no longer significantly pronounced throughout the infusion. This may be related to the
191 doses selected and the slow administration of the initial bolus. Moreover, such a reduction was
192 insufficient to promote clinical repercussions and remained within the appropriate range for the
193 species.

194 Opioid-related adverse effects such as excitation, increased motor activity, or muzzle
195 tremors were not observed in donkeys, differing from previous studies¹⁵ with horses, which
196 showed such signs. Narcotic analgesics have been associated with excitation or, as often stated,
197 unpredictable reactions in horses. Stimulation of the central nervous system and increased
198 locomotor capacity are highly predictable and dose-related responses after administration of
199 most narcotic analgesics to horses.¹⁸ Even today, there is a reluctance to use opioids in horses
200 due to possible adverse effects, one of which is decreased gastrointestinal motility.¹⁹ During the
201 study, all animals were evaluated for gastrointestinal motility before and after the infusions.
202 After the infusions (M60), gastrointestinal motility was evaluated within 24 h after drug
203 administration, presenting no changes in all animals.

204 All animals recovered from sedation 7.1 ± 2.4 minutes after stopping the continuous
205 infusion of xylazine and remifentanyl, being able to move with minimal ataxia. These data
206 corroborate a previous study⁷ in which the authors evaluated the blood concentrations of
207 remifentanyl during and after infusion in horses anesthetized with isoflurane and
208 dexmedetomidine, observing that the blood concentration of remifentanyl decreased rapidly
209 after the infusion, which is consistent with its short half-life (12.8 ± 2.1 min). The data suggest
210 that the likelihood of remifentanyl causing excitation in horses during the recovery period after
211 an intravenous infusion is low. This information can also be considered for donkeys, although
212 pharmacokinetic studies are necessary for the species.

213 **5 Conclusion**

214 The association of xylazine and remifentanil at the doses used caused adequate sedation
215 in donkeys from the northeastern region of Brazil during standing procedures. Remifentanil did
216 not cause excitation in the donkeys. Further studies are needed to confront the protocol with
217 painful stimuli.

218

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223

224 **Conflict of interest**

225 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

226

227 **Authors' contribution**

228 Valéria V. de Paula conceptualized, drafted, supervised the writing of the final version of the
229 manuscript, and developed the methodology. Kássia F. A. Damasceno contributed to the
230 original draft, data curation, investigation, and writing of the manuscript. Andressa N. Mouta
231 and Káthryn Nóbrega contributed to data curation, investigation, and writing of the manuscript.
232 Larissa S. Alves, Herbert Reis Aragão, and Jerson Marques Cavalcante contributed to data
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234

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